

First record of *Dieckmanniellus nitidulus* (Gyllenhal, 1838) (Coleoptera, Brentidae) from Altaiskii Krai, Western Siberia

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Abstract

The first record of *Dieckmanniellus nitidulus* (Gyllenhal, 1838) (Brentidae: Nanophyinae: Nanophyini) from Altaiskii Krai is given. The distribution map, illustrations and redescription of this species are presented.

Keywords

Curculionoidea, Nanophyinae, Nanophyini, weevil, fauna, new finding, Siberia

Introduction

Representatives of the tribe Nanophyini are distributed almost throughout the world (Alonso-Zarazaga and Lyal 1999). Six species from five genera were recorded in Siberia (Zherikhin 1981; Korotyayev 1984; Legalov and Opanassenko 2000; Galich and Legalov 2012; Legalov 2020). The genus *Dieckmanniellus* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1989 includes four species distributed in the West and Central Palaearctic (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017). It differs from related genera in the incompletely crenulate elytral interstria 8, strongly carinate metarostrium and very long tarsi (Alonso-

Zarazaga 1989). *Dieckmanniellus nitidulus* (Gyllenhal, 1838) was recorded in Tyva (Korotyayev 1984) and Novosibirsk region (Tshernyshev and Legalov 2008).

It is the first record of this species from Altaiskii Krai.

Materials and methods

Studied specimens are kept in the ISEA – Institute of Systematics and Ecology of Animals (Russia: Novosibirsk).

Photographs, descriptions and body measuring were performed using a Zeiss Stemi 2000-C dissecting stereomicroscope.

The terminology of weevil body is according to Lawrence et al. (2010) and Alonso-Zarazaga (1989). The systematics of studied taxa are based on Alonso-Zarazaga et al. (2017) and Legalov (2018).

Result

Superfamily Curculionoidea Latreille, 1802

Family Brentidae Billberg, 1820

Subfamily Nanophyinae Gistel, 1848

Tribe Nanophyini Gistel, 1848

Genus *Dieckmanniellus* Alonso-Zarazaga, 1989

Dieckmanniellus nitidulus (Gyllenhal, 1838)

Figs 1–3

Material examined. RUSSIA 1 ex. (ISEA), Altaiskii Krai, Klyuchevsky District, 4.2 km NW of Petukhi, S shore of Petukhovo lake, 52.25002° N, 79.48652° E, 17.VI.2022, A. Legalov; 1 ex. (ISEA), Novosibirsk Oblast, Karasuksky District, 20 km W of Karasuk, env. Troitskoe, 30.V.2007, S. Tshernyshev; 1 ex. (ISEA), Volgograd Oblast, east shore of Bulukhta Lake, 49.351° N, 46.116° E, 20.V.2021, R.Yu. Dudko; 2 ex. (ISEA), Volgograd Oblast, west shore of Elton Lake, 49.165° N, 46.564° E, 19-20.V.2021, R.Yu. Dudko; KAZAKHSTAN 1 ex. (ISEA), East Kazakhstan Region, 10 km SSW of Slavyanka, 8.V.1999, R. Dudko, V. Zichchenko; 5 ex. (ISEA), Jambyl Region, Karatau, 21.VII.1994, A.V. Boiko.

Description. Male. Body brownish-black, covered with narrow piliform white appressed scales. Scape, antennomeres 1-5, base of femora, tibiae, basal half of pro-tarsomere 1, meso- and metatarsomeres 1 yellow-brown. Elytra and apex of rostrum brownish. Rostrum curved, subcylindrical, subglabrous, carinate from antennal insertion to base, slightly shorter than head and pronotum combined. Antennal scrobes distinct. Forehead very narrow. Eyes large, rounded, not protruding from

contour of head, quite coarsely faceted. Vertex finely punctate. Temples short. Antennae geniculate, inserted laterally before middle of rostrum, rather long. Funicle 5-segmented. Scape long, curved in apical one third, reaching eye. Antennomere 2 suboval. Antennomere 3 long-conical, shorter and narrower than antennomere 2. Antennomere 4 conical, distinctly shorter and barely narrower than antennomere 3. Antennomeres 5 and 6 wide-conical. Antennomeres 5 shorter and wider than antennomere 4. Antennomere 6 shorter and wider than antennomere 5. Club noncompact, longer than antennomeres 2-6 combined. Pronotum almost campaniform, about 1.2 times as long as wide at apex, about 0.9 times as long as wide in middle and about 0.8 times as long as wide at base. Sides almost straight. Disk finely punctate. Greatest width at base. Scutellum very small, concealed. Elytra suboval, strongly convex, about 1.7 times as long as base width, about 1.4 times as long as wide in middle, about 2.0 times as long as wide in apical quarter, about 2.5 times as long as pronotum. Greatest width in middle. Base of elytra with granulate carina. Humeri flattened. Striae distinct. Interstriae wide, slightly convex, finely punctate. Interstria 8 incompletely crenulate. Elytral apices rounded separately. Pre- and post-coxal portions of prosternum short. Pro- and mesocoxal cavities rounded. Procoxal cavities contiguous. Mesocoxal cavities separated. Metacoxal cavities transversely extended. Andomen convex. Ventrites 1 and 2 fused, equal in length. Ventrite 1 slightly shorter than metacoxal length. Ventrites 3 and 4 equal in length, short. Ventrite 3 about 0.2 times as long as ventrite 2. Ventrite 5 about 5.0 times as long as ventrite 4. Legs long. Procoxae conical. Meso- and metacoxae convex. Trochanters elongate. Femora slightly clavate, separated from coxae, with two teeth. Tibiae almost straight, mucronate. Tarsi long, with erect setae dorsally. Tarsomere 1 elongate-conical. Tarsomere 2 wide-conical. Tarsomere 3 bilobed. Tarsomere 5 long-conical. Claws relatively large, fused at base, without teeth. Body length: 1.7 mm.

Remarks. This species develops on *Lythrum salicaria* L. (Lythraceae) (Smreczyński 1976) and *Frankenia tvinica* Lom. (Frankeniaceae) (Korotyaev 1984).

Distribution. North Africa, Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Siberia (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017). This species is found in Siberia (Novosibirsk Oblast, Altaiskii Krai, Tyva Republic) and East Kazakhstan (Fig. 4).

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Figure 1. *Dieckmanniellus nitidulus* from Altaiskii Krai, male, dorsal view. Scale bar 0.2 mm.

Figure 2. *Dieckmanniellus nitidulus* from Altaiskii Krai, male, lateral view. Scale bar 0.2 mm.

Figure 3. *Dieckmanniellus nitidulus* from Altaiskii Krai, male. a – aedeagus, dorsal view, b – aedeagus, lateral view, c – tegmen, dorsal view. Scale bar 0.1 mm.

Figure 4. Distribution of *Dieckmanniellus nitidulus* in Central Asia.

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